

The Effects of Religious Heritage on Water Bodies in India & Management of its Environment Impact

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Abstract

In India, water and water bodies have been an object of worship from time immemorial. They have diverse socio-religious uses and play a central role in many religious ceremonies and rites in India. Water is considered a purifier in most religions. Major faiths that incorporate ritual washing include Christianity, Hinduism, and Islam. Water, in addition to having ecological significance as a source & sustainer of life, plays a vital role in holy rituals or rites. Lakes and artificial reservoirs were used for activities like irrigation, washing and were sanctified and the waters were drawn only in times of drought or similar times of crisis. Their waters (*tirtham*) are believed to cleanse all sins. However, over the years, the ever increasing size of religious fairs and festivals which severely affect the purity of rivers and tanks and the increasing proclivities of the burgeoning Indian population to observe various rituals in rivers, without giving a care about the resultant water pollution, are causes for worry from perspectives of sanitation, hygiene and environmental protection. This research paper discusses the effect of religious heritage on water bodies and management of its impact on environment.

Key Words: Religious heritage of India, environmental impact, water management

Introduction

In India, water has been an object of worship from time immemorial. It has diverse socio-religious uses and plays a central role in many religious ceremonies and rites in India. Water is considered a purifier in most religions. Major faiths that incorporate ritual washing include Christianity, Hinduism, Sikhism and Islam. Some faiths use water especially prepared for religious purposes (holy water in some Christian denominations, *Amrita* in Sikhism and Hinduism). Many religions also consider particular sources or bodies of water to be sacred or at least auspicious. Water is often believed to have spiritual powers in Hinduism, the Ganges is also personified as a goddess, while Saraswati have been referred to as goddess in Vedas. They include “totemism” in which one or more species of water bodies are protected as spiritual ancestors, conserving certain species for rituals, keeping aside patches of forests and water bodies in the name of local deities and so on. **In Buddhism** the religion seeks spiritual awakening through meditation and wisdom. Rites are basically absent. Water, however is used in Buddhist funerals. **In Christianity**, water is intrinsically linked to baptism, a public declaration of faith and a sign of welcome into the Christian church. In the New Testament, the 'living water' or 'water of life' represents the spirit of God, that is, eternal life. **In Hinduism** water is imbued with powers of spiritual purification for Hindus. All temples are located near a water source, and followers are often expected to take a bath before entering the temple. Many pilgrimage sites are found on river banks; sites where two or even three rivers converge (“sangam”) are considered particularly sacred. While the ponds, lakes and artificial reservoirs were used for activities like irrigation, washing etc., the temple tanks were sanctified and the waters were drawn only in times of drought or similar times of crisis. If we consider religious importance the temple tanks are revered no less than the temple itself. Their waters are believed to cleanse all sins. In fact, devotees are required to wash their hands and feet in the temple

tank before entering the temple. The waters are also used to perform the daily ritual bath of the temple deity. Annual float festivals are conducted in the tanks, wherein the idol of the deity is floated around the tank on a decorated raft. However, the sacred conservation practices followed by local people, have come into focus of late due to their importance for influencing several delicate water ecosystems indirectly.

The following is a description of the religious and ecological influences of some of the important water bodies in India, starting with the most revered and important of these, namely, the river Ganga (or the Ganges in its Western iteration).

Table showing some of the sacred rivers, lakes and springs in India:

<u>SACRED RIVER</u>	<u>SACRED LAKE</u>	<u>SACRED HOT SPRING</u>
GANGA	HEMKUND	MANIKARAN
CHAMBAL	PUSKAR	TATTAPANI
BHAGIRATHI	MANIMAHESH	GAURIKUND
JHELUM	KHEHIOPALRI	
GODAVARI	GURUDONGHAR	
GANDAK	TSUMGO LAKE	
CAVERY		
KEISHNA		
MAHANADU		
NARMADA		
PHALGU		
GOMTI		
SHIPRA		
TAPTI		
YUMUNA		
KALIBAN		
TUNGABHADRA		

River Ganga

The actual geographical origin of the Ganges is the Gaumukh glacier in the state of Uttarakhand. Here, the river is known as Bhagirathi. The river Bhagirathi joins river Alaknanda, fed by the

glacier Satopani, to form the Ganges near Devprayag. The total length of the river is 2510km and its confluence with the Bay of Bengal is in West Bengal. It is India's most sacred water body and is personified in Hindu mythology as Goddess Ganga. Hindus believe that bathing in her holy waters would help wash away their sins and aid them in securing a place in the *swargaloka* (heaven). Mythologically, the river is believed to have originated when Brahma washed the feet of Lord Vishnu (during His incarnation as Vamana) using his kamandala or water pot. From this pot Ganga emerged. Ganga is believed to have brought down to earth by Bhagiratha. He prayed to Lord Brahma to let Ganga come down to earth and then go to patalaloka (underworld). Brahma agreed, and ordered Ganga to descend to earth. Ganga felt insulted and decided to sweep the whole earth as she fell from the heavens. Bhagiratha prayed to Lord Shiva to stop Ganga's descent and prevent calamitous floods on Earth.

Responding to Bhagirath's prayers Lord Shiva was supposed to have covered the entire sky with

his locks (*jata*) when the river fell from the heaven, so that not a drop would fall on earth. This manifestation of Lord Shiva is sometimes referred to as Gangadhar. After he fully captured her, he let her out in small streams. Realizing her foolishness, Ganga thereafter followed Bhagiratha wherever he went – down the mountains, across the plains and finally into the sea.

Ecological Significance of the Ganges

From the alpine forests in the Himalayas to the mangroves in its delta, the river Ganga supports a wide variety of flora and fauna including tigers, deer, leopards, crocodiles, turtles and storks. The river is also home to the Ganga river dolphins (*Platanista gangetia*), which is endemic to the Ganga-Brahmaputra river systems. It is considered one of the most endangered animals in the region. Although the spiritual purity of river Ganga has remained unchanged through ages, the physical aspects have deteriorated over the years due to over-exploitation of her waters. Various pollutants including cremated corpses, livestock carcasses, industrial wastes and raw sewage are discharged into the river every day. There have been many attempts to clean up the river (including the Ganga Action Plan launched by the Government of India way back in 1985), but none have been completely successful. Apart from the river, recent studies have shown that the Gangotri glacier, the source of the Ganga, has been retreating at an alarming rate. This has been mainly attributed to the increase in population, mass deforestation and global warming.

River Godavari

Religious Significance

Godavari is one of the most sacred rivers of India. The Godavari river is so named because, according to a mythical tale, it relieved the sage Gautama who lived on the Brahmagiri Hills at Triambakeshwar of the sin of killing a cow (“Gohatya”) unwittingly. The rishi worshipped Lord Shiva and requested him to bring Ganga to purify his hermitage. Lord Shiva, pleased with the rishi,

appeared as Triambaka and veered river Ganga to Triambakeshwar. Since the river was created by the prayers of Sage Gautama, she is also known here as Gautami.

Every twelve years, the Pushkaram fair is held on its banks Godavari, one of the most sacred rivers in India. Thousands of people have a holy dip in the sacred waters of the river to purify themselves of all their sins.

Ecological Significance

The Coringa mangrove forests in the Godavari delta are the second largest mangrove formation in the country, next only to the Sunderbans in its expanse. Part of this has been declared as the Coringa Wildlife Sanctuary; it is famous for its reptiles, and is also an important habitat to a wide variety of fish and crustaceans. These mangrove forests also act as barriers against cyclones, tropical storms and tidal waves and protect the nearby villages. The Godavari-Krishna basin also happen to be one of the main nesting sites of the endangered Olive Ridley turtles.

River Jhelum

The Jhelum originates from a spring called Verinag which is located in the South Eastern part of Kashmir. The length of the river is 725km. and it ends in Pakistan.

Religious Significance

Also known as the Vitasta by ancient Indians in the Vedic times, the river Jhelum originates from .The Kashmiri people (especially the Kashmiri pandits) worship the river (Vitasta) which is identified with Goddess Parvathi (a form of Durga) in the Hindu religion. Many legends are associated with the name and origin of Jhelum river in Kashmir valley. According to the “Nilamata Purana”, Sage Kashyap drained the Satisar to put an end to the water demon who was harassing valley dwellers and killing them.

Ecological Significance

The Jhelum is the main waterway of the valley of Kashmir. The Jhelum river is ecologically significant for diverse ecosystems, unique flora and fauna, water supply, hydroelectric power, irrigation and protected areas like three national parks, eight conservation reserves, nine wetland conservation reserves and eight wild life sanctuaries.

River Kaveri (Cauvery)

The Kaveri river originates from Talakaveri at Western Ghat. The length of the river is 765 km and its confluence lies in the Bay of Bengal (Kaveri pattinam) at Taminadu.

Religious Significance

According to Hindu mythology, Vishnumaya or Lopamudra, daughter of Lord Brahma, was born as the child of the Kavera Muni. Later she was married to Sage Agasthaya. Later, she became the river Kaveri in order to serve mankind.

Devout Hindus refer to the Kaveri (Cauvery) river as Dakshin Ganga or the ‘Ganges of the South’. The river is personified as the Goddess Kaveri Amman, and there are several shrines along the course of the river where the goddess is worshipped.

Ecological Significance

The river basin supports a wide variety of organisms, many of which are endemic to the region. It is the natural habitat of many fish varieties including the Mahseer, one of the popular game varieties.

The Kaveri river is one of the important rivers in our country. It, along with its major tributaries (Kabini, Noyyal, Bhavani, Amaravathy, Lokapavani, Kapila, Hemavathi etc.), passes through important cities and towns including Bangalore, Mysore, Coimbatore, Trichy and Erode and acts as a lifeline to the people of Karnataka and Tamil Nadu. However, the ever burgeoning population of these urban areas and scant regard for maintaining ecological purity of rivers, along with large-scale water extraction and other activities near the river banks have seriously affected the water quantity and quality of Kaveri.

River Narmada

The Narmada originates from Amarkantak Hills in the state of Madhya Pradesh. The length of the river is 1289 km. and it flows into the Arabian Sea. It is the largest west flowing river in India.

Religious Significance

River Narmada happens to be one of the most sacred rivers in our country and is revered as a Goddess by people living along the banks of the river and many consider her to be holier than the Ganges. Thousands of pilgrims circumambulate the river during the annual Naramada parikrama. There are many holy places (“thirthas”) on the banks of the river, including the famous Maheshwar and Omkareshwar temples.

The river is closely associated with Lord Shiva. There are many mythological tales that describe the origin of the river. According to one, the river was formed from the perspiration of Lord Shiva, while performing the “tandava” (Lord Shiva’s cosmic dance of destruction). Naturally formed Shiva lingams or banas are found in the river and these stones are considered sacred by devout Hindus.

Ecological Significance

The Narmada supports a large variety of aquatic life including the marsh crocodile and the mahsa fish. Although the dry deciduous forests along the river is not really exceptional in terms of biodiversity or endemic species, the region is still a prime natural habitat of large animals – tiger, gaur, wild dog, sloth bear and black buck, to name a few. The region’s vegetation includes culturally and economically important species like teak, bamboo, mahua, tendu etc. Hence, this region plays an important role in the long-term conservation of these species. The Narmada river is one of the least polluted and disturbed waterways in the country.

Hemkund Lake

Hemkund lake, about 2 km in circumference, is located at a height of 4329 meters above MSL and is fed by the *Hathi Parvat* and *Sapt Rishi* glaciers. It is encircled by seven snow peaks known as *Saptashringa* peaks; the images of the peaks reflect on the clear, still waters of the lake.

Religious significance:

The holy lake is associated with the tenth Sikh Guru, Guru Gobind Singh who mentioned in his autobiographical poem '*Bichittar Natak*' that in his previous life he meditated on the shore of a lake that was surrounded by seven snow-capped mountains. The banks of the Hemkund Lake are presumed to be this place. A dip in the waters of the lake is considered sacred by the Sikhs. The star-shaped gurudwara (Sri Hemkund sahib) located on the banks of the lake is one of the most important pilgrimage sites for the Sikhs. Hemkund is also sacred for the Hindus. According to

Hindu mythology, Hemkund is where Lakshman (Lord Rama's brother) did his penance. The mythological name for Hemkund is 'Lokpal'. There is also a temple dedicated to Laxman on the banks of the lake. The river flowing through this valley along the path from Gobindghat to Gobinddham is called Lakshman Ganga.

Manikaran hot springs

Location: Parvati Valley (Northeast of Bhuntar in Kulu District), Himachal Pradesh at an altitude of 1760 meters

Several hot water springs emerge at various locations at Manikaran along the Parvati river. There is no sulphur or iron mixed in the waters, but it is said to contain radioactive elements such as uranium and radium. The water from the springs are so hot that rice, pulses and vegetables can be cooked with it. The springs are also famous for their miraculous healing powers. People come here from different parts of India for taking a dip in the spring water, which is believed to cure ailments such as rheumatism, gout and muscular pain.

Religious significance:

Manikaran is a well-known pilgrimage centre for the Hindus. There are several temples in Manikaran, the most prime one being the one dedicated to Lord Raghunatha (Rama) that was constructed by Raja Jagat Singh in the 17th century. Though there is no hard historical evidence, the *pandas* (priests) of the temple claim that the idol of Rama was brought from Ayodhya and installed here. There is another very old temple at Manikaran dedicated to Lord Siva. It suffered extensive damage during the 1905 earthquake and got tilted like the tower of Pisa. Manikaran is also held sacred by the Sikhs because of its association with Guru Nanak and there is a famous gurudwara - Sri Guru Nanak Dev Ji Gurudwara here. Devotees visiting the Gurudwara take a holy dip in the hot water of the springs.

Khecheopalri Lake

Khecheopalri lake (known locally to the Sikkimese as the Tsho-Sho-Tsho lake, also known as the ‘wish fulfilling lake’) is located in the West Sikkim district at an altitude of about 2000 meters on a bifurcation on the road between Gyalshing and Yuksam. The water in this lake is crystal clear. Not even a leaf can be seen floating on the water surface although there is a dense forest surrounding it. According to legends if a leaf falls on the surface of the water it is picked up by a bird.

The lake is considered to be sacred both by the Buddhists and the Hindus of Sikkim. From the vantage point of higher ground the contours of the lake look like a footprint – believers hold that it is Shiva’s footprint. The placid waters of the lake are visited each year by many pilgrims and tourists. The lake is surrounded by colourful prayer flags. No water sport or other recreational activities are allowed here. The lake is surrounded by a dense forest cover of temperate vegetation and bamboo and is an important habitat for several bird species. Birds including Baer’s Pochard duck (*Aythya baeri*), wintering Merganser ducks (*Mergus merganser*), Little Grebe (*Tachybaptus ruficollis*), Mallard (*Anas platyrhynchos*), Common Teal (*Anas crecca*) and Tufted Pochard (*Aythya fuligula*) have been sighted around Lake Khecheopalri.

Pushkar Lake

Pushkar lake, covering an area of about 5 kms, is an artificial lake created in the 12th century when a dam was built across the headwaters of the Luni river.

There are nearly 400 temples and shrines (including the famous Brahma temple) around the holy Pushkar lake. It is surrounded by 52 ghats, many of which have unique legendary importance. Lord Vishnu is said to have appeared at the Varah Ghat in the avtar of a boar. Brahma took a bath here and performed Yajna at the Brahma Ghat, accompanied by Vishnu and Mahadev. Guru Govind Singh chose this site for reciting the sacred Guru Granth Sahib. The ashes of Mahatma Gandhi were immersed at the Gau Ghat which was subsequently renamed as the Gandhi Ghat.

Religious Significance:

The Great Hindu epics of Mahabharata and Ramayana make references to Pushkar, regarded to be the Adi Tiratha. According to legends the lake was created by Lord Brahma. A demon named Vajra Nabha had killed Brahma's children. In revenge, Brahma struck him with a lotus flower. Vajra Nabha died in the impact, and the petals of the lotus fell at three places. One of them was Pushkar, where a lake sprang into being. Brahma is supposed to have performed sacrifice at this lake on Kartik Purnima (the full moon day of the Kartik month). Thousands of pilgrims come to bathe in the waters of the lake during the festival of Kaartika Poornima in November. The mystical water is widely believed to cure skin diseases.

Ecological Significance:

Pushkar lake is rich in fish and other aquatic life. Sadly, in the recent past, the lake has become polluted due to developmental activities around the lake, excessive tourism, cattle fairs, poorly planned sewer systems, submergence of ashes and performance of religious rituals. Due to a

gradual depletion of water level in the lake, the raw water requirement of the lake has to be fulfilled through tube wells.

JHAM

Role of water bodies in water conservation in ancient India

India has a long tradition of building dams, canals and tanks stretching for centuries to benefit humanity (Chakravarthy et al. 2006). Every village in Sindhu-Sarasvati river basin of the ancient Indus valley civilization had a tank called pushkarni or source of fertility. Hindu scriptures such as the Vedas, Upanishads, Bhagavad Gita and Ramayana mention the sacredness of water (Radhakrishnan 1953). Rig Veda states, "waters from heaven or those which flow or those which

come from digging or those which of their own accord come out as spring, speeding toward the ocean, those which are bright and pure, O Goddess, protect me" (Asthaka VII-49-2; Muller 2011). Similarly, in Bhagavad Gita, Lord Krishna tells the warrior King Arjuna, "O Arjuna, I give heat, I send forth and withhold rain, I am alone immortal and death, and all that exist in the manifest present, un-manifest past and un-manifest future" (chapter 9, verse 19; Tapasyananda 2006). The epic Ramayana defines the water cycle as, "the sun's rays have drunk the water of the seas and carrying it as an embryo for 9 months, is giving out the elixir of life" (Kiskindha 28:3; Dutt 2009). The scriptures even reveal methods to build dams across rivers and aqueducts (Rangarajan 1992; Barah 1996). Archeological ruins at Dholavira in Gujarat state show evidence of a planned city with sophisticated drainage system located in the midst of two rivers (Bisht 1991). Archeologists have unearthed a huge reservoir (263 ft long, 39 ft wide and 24 ft deep) near the entrance of the fortress. A total of 16 reservoirs were found in a 10 hectare area with a capacity to store 350,000 cbm of water and interconnected with an intricate network of aqueducts large enough to store water year round (Mcintosh 2007). Water-harvesting systems can also be seen along Naneghat in the Western Ghats (Barah 1996). Baked earthen pipes and tunnels that run underground to transport water to distant places can be seen at Burhanpur (Madhya Pradesh), Golkunda, Bijapur (Karnataka) and Aurangabad (Maharashtra). The Vijayanagar Kingdom (1336-1564) in south India was known for its river-based irrigation. The 15th century King Krishna Deva Raya believed that the kingdom would prosper only when it had built dams.

Efforts to Refresh Polluted Rivers: From cradle to cremation:

All these examples show how a common thread of respect and tradition has intertwined rivers, lakes, dams and springs with the peoples of India, cutting across regions and religions from time immemorial. In spite of this, modern India faces the grim reality of a widespread crisis of access to clean water. With the population soaring over 1.2 billion, poor attention to the threat of

environmental degradation brought about by rapid and often uncontrolled urbanization and the mismanagement of rivers have made the country one of the most water starved in the world. Rivers have become dump sites for waste and untreated sewage though the Hindu religion expressly prohibits such abusive practice (Agoramoorthy 2012). India's Pollution Control Board estimates that only 30% of municipal sewage undergoes treatment while 68.5 million cbm of untreated sewage and industrial waste are dumped in different water bodies without caring about the horrific environmental damage caused by such wanton acts.

Consequently, diarrhea alone causes more than 1,600 deaths daily, and 21 % of India's communicable diseases can be attributed to unsafe drinking water (Agoramoorthy 2012). Each year, innumerable Hindu devotees take a dip in the holy Ganges not only to wash away their sins but also, they believe, to open the gateways to heaven after death. Sadly,

the Ganges as a result has become profoundly polluted with toxic waste. Realizing the crisis, the Union Government started an ambitious USD 4 billion project to ensure no untreated sewage/industrial runoff enters the 2,500-km-long river. In order to save the degenerating rivers across India, several movements have emerged in recent decades. For example, the north India based 'Save Ganga Movement' is a popular nonviolent crusade supported by Hindu monks, spiritual leaders, writers and social activists, and it fights for its cleanup. India's Prime Minister, Mr. Narendra Modi, has showed personal interest in the Ganges clean up. He has been elected as a Member of Parliament from the sacred Hindu city of Varanasi, and he adores the river as 'Mother Ganga' like millions of Hindu devotees. Besides, the country's prominent Hindu religious leaders were invited to advise the Prime Minister on how to tackle the Ganges clean up (Das 2014). Yamuna - the largest tributary of the Ganges - is another dying holy river. Hindu religious devotees revere Yamuna because of its association with Lord Krishna—the incarnation of Vishnu. Several non-profit organizations and local government agencies are committed to clean up this religiously important river in north India. Similarly, the Save Narmada Movement is a noted non-government

agency that fights for the rights of millions of displaced people by the construction of large dams. The arguments for and against the construction of large dams continue to this day, with environmentally conscious people being most vociferous against such constructions. The holy river Cauvery in south India is also facing distress. The Karnataka State Pollution Control Board has blamed untreated sewage discharge and garbage dumping as causes for the crisis. Environmentally conscious citizens in Karnataka have started campaigning to save the river from further destruction.

Management of environmental impact of water body pollution:

It is heartening to note that the Ministry of Environment Forest & Climate change has recently released detailed project reports (DPR) on projects worthy rupees 19000 crore for the rejuvenation of 13 major rivers (namely Jhelum, Chenab, Ravi, Beas, **Sutlej, Yamuna, Brahmaputra, Narmada, Godavari, Mahanadi, Krishna, Kauvery, and Luni**) in India through forestry intervention, modelled in line with the National Mission for Clean Ganga in 2015-2016. It is worthwhile to know that these 13 rivers cover a basin area of 18,90,110 Square km. in total and represent a massive 57.45% geographical area of our country. The total length of these 13 rivers is 42830 km and they have 202 tributaries. The document proposes forestry intervention including different types of trees (both for logging and fruits), medicinal plants, grasses, shrubs and fuel fodder. The project had broad objectives of ‘**Aviral Dhara**’ (uninterrupted flow), ‘**Nirmal Dhara**’ (clean flow of water), and ecological rejuvenation through a multi-disciplinary holistic approach. The potential benefits include an **increase of forest cover across these thirteen riverscapes, sequestration of CO₂, groundwater, beside a boost to local employment and realization of the international commitments of creating additional carbon sink of 2.5-3 billion tons of CO₂.**

Also as a part of Namami Gange Mission 2.0 four major projects were completed in the first quarter of 2024. These include one for the Interception, Diversion and Treatment works for abatement of pollution of river Ganga at Mirzapur, **Ghazipur, Bareilly and Bisalpur Road in Uttar Pradesh**. These projects use the advances sequestering batch reactor technology and by treating waste water and cleaning up the rivers will benefit a large population of the cities along the banks of the rivers.

Conclusion

In India water bodies (rivers, lakes, springs etc.) have diverse socio-religious uses and often play a central role in many religious ceremonies and rites. Almost all rivers, lakes, springs are attributed some degree of holiness and are often **associated with the local pantheon of Gods and Goddesses**. They have environmental influences too and sometimes their religious influences can be detrimental to their environmental ones. Over the past few decades environmentally conscious people have woken up to the negative environmental impact of the socio-religious uses of water bodies and the Government have also begun to take some corrective measures. These measures, for lack of seriousness, funding and poor participation from the public were half-hearted at best and could produce only marginal effects initially; However, over the past several years these projects have begun to gather steam and, if these are coupled with increased public awareness and participation, we can hope to see some visible improvements in the fate of these water bodies in the not too distant future.

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